

maps of the field have been created using spectral indices at a resolution of 0.5 mm/pixel using the images captured by the DSLR cameras, and 2.5 mm/pixel using the images captured by the other cameras.

During the last survey of the field, 100 plants were marked to be later identified in the images. These plants were collected separately and taken to the laboratory to undergo a spectral analysis with a hyperspectral camera and a molecular analysis using specific real-time PCR, to determine the presence or absence of infection in the leaves and compare them to the maps created by the robot.